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Evaluation of Annual Effective Dose from Radon-²²² in Surface and Stream Water Samples from Kaltungo Area, Gombe State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Ubiquitous nature, along with the detrimental health impact of radon (²²²Rn), has led to the investigation of its activity concentration in the various environmental mediums, including bodies of water. This work was conducted to estimate the annual effective dose of inhalation due to ²²²Rn in Stream and some surface water around Kaltungo area, Gombe State, Nigeria. ²²²Rn activity concentration was measured using RAD7 alpha detector. The annual effective dose for inhalation was evaluated using the measured ²²²Rn activity concentration in water. The activity concentration of ²²²Rn in water varies from 80 ± 110 to 5400 ± 1100 mBq l⁻¹ in surface and Stream water respectively. The measured activity concentrations in the samples were found to be below the EPA and WHO maximum permissible limit for ²²²Rn in Water of 1100 mBq l⁻¹ and 10⁵ mBq l⁻¹ respectively. The highest value of ²²²Rn activity concentration was measured in Stream water discharging from granitic rocks Aquifer. While the lowest value was measured in surface water. The values of an annual effective dose of inhalation, due to ²²²Rn in Stream water, were found to range from 0.998 to 5.139 μ S y⁻¹ with a mean value of 2.15 μ S y⁻¹, while in the surface water the values range from 0.076 to 1.140 μ S y⁻¹ with a mean value of 0.423 μ S y⁻¹. The inhalation doses estimated were found to be well below the recommended limit set by UNSCEAR of 1260 μ Sv y⁻¹.

Keywords: Radon in water; Annual Effective Dose, Stream water; surface water; type of aquifer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Radon is an inert radioactive gas that is ubiquitous within our environment and exists in various quantities. Radon (²²²Rn) that emerge from the ²³⁸U decay series is considered the most significant isotope due to its long half-life (3.82 days) in comparison to other isotopes of radon (Auwal et al., 2025). The dissolved ²²²Rn in water mainly originate from ²²⁶Ra that, either dissolve in water or localized in a porous and permeable rock aquifer or soil materials in contact with water. When ²²²Rn atoms are produced in soil or rocks they have the potency to be expelled from the soil grain by alpha-recoil and transported to groundwater or void air and seep through the atmosphere (Abdallah et al., 2007; Somlai et al., 2007; Tabar and Yakut, 2014; Marques et al., 2004).

²²²Rn concentration in groundwater varies according to the geological formation of a given aquifer (Abdallah et al., 2007; Duggal et al., 2013; Salih et al., 2002; Jobbágy et al., 2010; Przylibski and Gorecka, 2014). The movement and concentration level of ²²²Rn within a bedrock is anisotropic, which mainly relies on the type of rock, physical condition as well as geochemistry of the rock aquifer (Michel, 1990; Durrani, 1999; Zhuo et al., 2001; De Oliveira et al., 2001; Aleissa et al., 2012). Numerous studies were conducted to investigate the relationship between ²²²Rn activity concentration

in water and the geological environment (Auwal et al., 2025). Elevated ^{222}Rn levels are commonly found in ground and Stream water discharging from metamorphic and granitic rocks (Michel, 1990; Durrani, 1999; Weise et al., 2001; Aleissa et al., 2012; Freiler et al., 2016). Moreno et al., (2014), reported that Felsic granites contain an excessive concentration of the parent element of the ^{222}Rn decay series (^{238}U). The radiological risk of lung cancer due to inhalation of ^{222}Rn and its progeny is well recognised (WHO, 2009). ^{222}Rn undergoes alpha decay, with the emission of two daughters (^{214}Po and ^{218}Po) that contribute, to more than 90% of the radiation dose due to ^{222}Rn exposure (Auwal et al., 2025; Marques et al., 2004). An exposure to ^{222}Rn accounts for more than 50% (1.26 mSv/y) of the average annual exposure due to natural source (UNSCEAR, 2008). The associated hazard of ^{222}Rn ingestion is less than that of inhalation of ^{222}Rn that exhale into the air from the same water (Crawford-Brown, 1990); (DURRIDGE Company Inc., 2011); (Duggal et al., 2020). Therefore estimation of inhalation dose due to ^{222}Rn in water is considered in this research

Intrusive igneous rocks of granitic origin occupy approximately 27% of the total land area in the Kaltungo region of Gombe State (Auwal et al., 2025; Saleh et al., 2015). Most of the stream water in the study area are situated within these intrusive rock zones. Given this geological setting, it is essential to quantify the concentration of radon-222 (^{222}Rn) in these water to safeguard public health. Furthermore, assessing the annual effective doses from ^{222}Rn inhalation is crucial, as it constitutes a major component of the total lifetime radiological exposure in humans (Bem et al., 2014). This study was therefore undertaken to evaluate the annual effective doses due to ^{222}Rn in stream and surface water of Kaltungo, Gombe State, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Kaltungo area, Gombe State has geological formations grouped according to their geological age broadly as Cretaceous-Jurassic, Devonian, Intrusive rocks, Permian, Quaternary, Tertiary, and Triassic geological formations, According to the geological map of peninsular Nigeria (Director-General of Geological Survey Nigeria, 1985). Table 1 below presents the geological formations of the water sampling locations.

Table 1 Geology of the water sampling locations

Geology	Composition
Intrusive rocks	Undifferentiated intrusive rocks, classified as granite biotite
Triassic	Combination of undifferentiated shale, siltstone, sandstone, mudstone, and minor limestone lenses

2.2 Sampling

A total of eleven (11) water samples were collected, five (5) samples from the Stream water source and six (6) from other surface water sources in the vicinity of residential areas with the view that these water sources have potential exposure of ^{222}Rn to the environs. The water samples were collected directly from the source by immersing the 250 ml glass vials (of the RAD H₂O kit) into the water source ensuring that no air bubbles entered into the sampling bottles. The 250 ml glass vials have a radon extraction efficiency of 94%. The samples collected was measured within less than 10 hours from sampling time to avoid loss of radon from the water samples.

2.3 Measurement of ^{222}Rn in water

Measurement of ^{222}Rn activity concentration in water was conducted using the RAD7 alpha detector coupled with RAD H₂O. Prior to measurement, the equipment was thoroughly purged with an outdoor air for several minutes to ensure that the equipment's humidity drops below 5% and it is free from old radon. After purging, the measurement was conducted with the equipment set at Wat250 protocol. The time taking to aerate the samples, equilibrium rest, and counting of the samples was 30 minutes at the end of the last counting cycle the printer attached to the detector print out the average radon readings counted, a bar chart of the readings and a cumulative spectrum. The average ^{222}Rn activity concentration in the water was calculated and stored automatically by the system. The RAD7 was later connected to the PC, and the measurement results were downloaded to the RAD-Capture where necessary corrections are done (DURRIDGE Company Inc., 2011). The coordinates of the sampling locations were recorded using a global positioning system (GPS) which were later plotted on the map of the geological survey of the study area to identify the geological formation of the water samples.

2.4 Annual Effective dose due to ²²²Rn water

The annual effective dose of inhalation due to ²²²Rn in water was calculated using the parameters adopted from UNSCEAR (2000):

$$D_{inh} (\mu Sv y^{-1}) = AC_{RnW} \times R_{aw} \times E_f \times T_o \times DCF \tag{1}$$

Where D_{inh} is the effective dose for inhalation, AC_{RnW} is the activity concentration of ²²²Rn in water (Bq l⁻¹), R_{aw} is the ratio of ²²²Rn in the air to ²²²Rn in water (10⁻⁴), E_f is the equilibrium factor between ²²²Rn and its progenies (0.6), T_o is the average occupancy time per individual (1760 h y⁻¹), and DCF is the dose conversion factor for ²²²Rn exposure (9 nSv (Bq h m⁻³)⁻¹) (UNSCEAR, 2000).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 ²²²Rn activity concentration in water

The measured ²²²Rn activity concentration in water samples was evaluated. Table 2, Presents the variation of the data for ²²²Rn activity concentration in Stream and surface water with the type of rock aquifer identified in the case of Stream water. The activity concentration of ²²²Rn in water varies, from 80 ± 110 to 5400 ± 1100 mBq l⁻¹ in surface and Stream water respectively. The highest ²²²Rn activity concentration of 5400 ± 1100 mBq l⁻¹ was obtained from the Stream water samples of Kaltungo area, Gombe State, Nigeria. While the lowest activity concentration of 80 mBq l⁻¹ was observed in the surface water samples from in Kaltungo area, Gombe State. The measured values of ²²²Rn in water were all found to be below the maximum contaminant level (MCL) set by the United States Environmental Protection Agency of 11100 mBq l⁻¹. This MCL is based on inhalation risk estimates of 10⁻⁴ as the ratio of radon in water to air, which is in agreement with the estimated lifetime cancer risk of 2 × 10⁻⁴ (Krishan et al., 2015).

Table 2 Measured ²²²Rn activity concentration in water and type water source

Source of water	AC _{RnW} (mBq l ⁻¹)	Aquifer type
Lake	690 ± 370	-
River	1480 ± 520	-
River	80 ± 110	-
River	230 ± 190	-
River	270 ± 240	-
Sea	200 ± 200	-
Stream	2450 ± 640	Intrusive rock
Stream	5400 ± 1100	Intrusive rock
Stream	1050 ± 420	Intrusive rock
Stream	1270 ± 510	Intrusive rock
Stream	1200 ± 500	Triassic formation

Figure 1: Measured ²²²Rn activity concentration in water and type water source

Table 3 present the statistical summary of the activity concentration of ²²²Rn in Stream and surface water. The values of ²²²Rn in Stream water varies from 1050 ± 420 to 5400 ± 1100 mBq l⁻¹ with a mean value of 2264 mBq l⁻¹, while the values of ²²²Rn measured in surface water vary from 80 ± 110 to 1480 ± 520 mBq l⁻¹ with a mean value of 492 mBq l⁻¹. The mean value of ²²²Rn activity concentration measured in Stream water by this study is about five times higher than the mean value obtained from the surface water. The high value obtained from the Stream water can be associated to reason that, the Stream water are mostly discharging from an aquifer of intrusive granitic rocks. (UNSCEAR, 2000), reported that granitic rocks contain a high concentration of natural radionuclides and this accounts for the reason why most of our Stream water samples have higher ²²²Rn activity concentration.

Table 3 Summary statistics of ²²²Rn activity concentration in Stream and surface water

	N	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
²²² Rn in Surface (mBq l ⁻¹)	6	493	214.2	526.9	80	1480
²²² Rn in Stream (mBq l ⁻¹)	5	2264	820.4	1834.7	1050	5400

Table 4 present the result of this study with that of other studies from different countries for ²²²Rn activity concentration in Stream and surface water. The table shows that the data range for this study of ²²²Rn activity concentration in Stream water is comparable with that of Tabar and Yakut (Tabar and Yakut, 2014).

Table 4 Comparing the measured ^{222}Rn activity concentration in water with other studies

Location/ Country	Method	^{222}Rn in water Range * 10^3 (mBq l ⁻¹)		Reference
		Stream water	Surface water	
Kaltungo, Gombe State/Nigeria	RAD7	1.1 to 5.4	0.1 to 1.5	This study
Southwest coastal region of Peninsular Nigeria	RAD7			(Ismail et al., 2021)
Perak/ Nigeria	RAD7	0.04 to 0.62	0.33 to 3.98	(Nuhu et al., 2020)
Muzaffarabad/Pakistan	RAD7	0.3 to 34.4	NM	Khan et al. (Khan et al., 2019)
Istanbul/ Turkey	AlphaGU ARD	1.6 to 14	NM	Doğan et al. (Doğan et al., 2018)
South of Catalonia/ Spain	LSC	1.4 to 104.9	NM	Fonollosa et al. (Fonollosa et al., 2016)
Shenzhen city/ South China	AlphaGU ARD (PQ2000)	3.1 to 82.0	0.15 to 0.51	Li et al. (Li et al., 2015)
Southern Kohat Plateau/ Pakistan	RAD7	1.1 to 25.1	NM	Khattak et al. (Khattak et al., 2014)
Yalova basin/ Turkey	RAD 7	0.21 to 5.82	NM	Tabar and Yakut (Tabar and Yakut, 2014)
Balakot and Mansehra/Pakistan	LUK-WG-1001	12.73 to 22.90	4.99 to 11.79	Khan et al. (Khan et al., 2009)
Transylvania /Romania	LUK-VR	2 to 129.3	0.5 to 10	Cosma et al. (Cosma et al., 2008)
Spain	HPGe	4 to 1868		Ródenas et al. (Ródenas et al., 2008)

NM: Not measured

3.1 An annual effective dose of inhalation due to ^{222}Rn in water

The annual effective dose of inhalation due to ^{222}Rn is defined by (UNSCEAR, 2018) as $1260 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$. The summary statistics of the annual effective dose of inhalation due to ^{222}Rn in water are presented in Table 5. The estimated values range from 1.0 to $5.100 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ with a mean value of $2.205 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ for the measured Stream water, and 0.080 to $1.140 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ with a mean value of $0.423 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ for surface water. The values of the annual effective dose of inhalation for all the water samples fall below the recommended level of $1260 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ set by (UNSCEAR, 2008).

Table 5 Summary statistics of the calculated effective dose of inhalation

	N	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
D_{inh} for Stream wasters ($\mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$)	5	2.205	0.764	1.708	1.000	5.130
D_{inh} for surface wasters ($\mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$)	6	0.423	0.165	0.403	0.080	1.140

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted to estimate the annual effective dose of inhalation due to ^{222}Rn in Stream and surface water of Kaltungo, Gombe State. The measured ^{222}Rn activity concentration has mean values of 2264 mBq l^{-1} and 492 mBq l^{-1} in Stream and surface water, respectively. The measured activity concentrations of ^{222}Rn were found to be below the maximum contaminant level set by the US environmental protection agency and world health organization. The calculated effective dose of inhalation has mean values of $2.205 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ and $0.423 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ for Stream and surface water respectively, the estimated values were found to be below the recommended limit of UNSCEAR ($1260 \mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$). Therefore, exposure to the measured water sources is considered to be within the safe limit from the radiological point of view.

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